

In situ hydrothermal synthesis of 2D zinc-tetrazolate framework and hydrothermal conversion of framework to ZnO nano and micro-structures

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Abstract

5-(4-Chlorobenzyl)-1H-tetrazole ligand (HL) was synthesized by Sharpless method. Furthermore, a tetrazole based Zn(II) metal organic framework, $[Zn(L)_2]_n$ (1), (L = 5-(4-Chlorobenzyl)tetrazolate), was synthesized by in situ reaction of 4-chlorobenzeneacetonitrile, NaN_3 and $ZnCl_2$ under hydrothermal conditions. Both compounds are structurally characterized by elemental analysis, IR, and single crystal X-ray diffraction. Compound 1 displays undulated 2D layers, sql/Shubnikov tetragonal plane net with (44.62) point symbol. Fluorescence measurements and thermogravimetric analysis of 1 were also performed. In addition, we describe here a complex precursor, hydrothermal route to prepare ZnO nano and micro structures. The effects of reaction temperature and pH on the growth process and morphology of ZnO nano and micro structures were investigated. Finally, a possible growth mechanism is proposed. The obtained samples have been characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX).

Keywords: hydrothermal syntheses, metal organic framework, tetrazole, Zn(II), ZnO nano and micro structures

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